
Negotiating Sense, Sensibility, and Society: Marriage as a Societal Agreement and Personal Pursuit in Jane Austen's Novels

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ABSTRACT

The paper “Negotiating Sense, Sensibility and Society: Marriage as a Societal Agreement and Personal Pursuit in Jane Austen’s Novels” elaborates the multilayered portrayal of marriage in the novels viz., *Pride and Prejudice*, *Sense and Sensibility*, *Mansfield Park* and *Northanger Abbey* by Jane Austen. It highlights the personal desires and social expectation of the early nineteenth century British society. From “*Happiness is an entirely a matter of chance*” from *Pride and Prejudice* to the bitter rejection faced by Catherine Morland due to dowry expectations in *Northanger Abbey*, Jane Austen’s works advocate for marriage that balances practical wisdom with emotional connection. This paper “Negotiating Sense, Sensibility and Society: Marriage as a Societal Agreement and Personal Pursuit in Jane Austen’s Novels” will elaborate marriage as a social necessity due to parental influence, judgments of the society, economic interest and social prudence. In her novel, the art of “catching” a good husband often hinges on social skills and self-presentation.

Introduction

“It is universally acknowledged, that a single man in possession of a good fortune, must be in want of a wife.” (Pride and Prejudice)

Jane Austen’s novels has remained reflective commentaries on the social, economic, and emotional facets of marriage in early nineteenth century England. Through *Pride and Prejudice*, *Sense and Sensibility*, *Mansfield Park* and *Northanger Abbey*, Jane Austen explores the difficulties faced by women where marriage is the primary route to social respectability, precise decorum and financial security. Her novels reveal the tensions between expectations of the society and individual desires.

Marriage as a Social Necessity

David Daiches states that Austen’s approach is *“neither romanticism nor sentimentality, but shows a remarkable insight into the relation between social convention and individual temperament.”* (Daiches, 744). In Austen’s society, marriage is very important for women’s futures, sometimes, the only available “respectable” option if they lack either wealth or beauty. The anxiety around securing such beneficial match is captured through character of Mrs. Jennings, an outspoken widow in *Sense and Sensibility*, who remarks on the value of unions where *“HE was rich, and SHE was handsome”* (*Sense and Sensibility*, Chapter VIII). She refers marriage as a practical affair, in which man should be rich and women must be attractive depicting both money and beauty as key factors in the institution of marriages. This societal pressure frames a backdrop where women are expected to conform to narrowly defined roles, a reality Austen both depicts and scrutinizes.

Parental Influence on Marriage in Austen’s Novels

Parental influence is a recurrent theme in the novels of Jane Austen. It demonstrates how marriage is also a matter of family strategy. Mrs. Ferrars’s firmness on a wealthy match for Edward clashes with his personal wishes. In *Northanger Abbey*, General Tilney’s reaction to Catherine Morland’s financial status, *“he immediately sent her away without any money”* (*Northanger Abbey*, Chapter 30). In *Pride and Prejudice* as well, Lady Catherine insisted Anne to marry Mr. Darcy because of his social status and wealth. Even the obsession of Mrs. Bennet of marrying off her daughters to wealthy suitable has been clearly depicted. However, Austen’s heroines often resisted these kinds of restrictions and pressure of parents. They often seemed to seek marriages based on love rather than financial advantage.

The conflict between mercenary and love marriages illuminates much of Austen's narrative tension. Maria Bertram in *Mansfield Park* views marriage as "a duty" and a route to "a larger income" (*Mansfield Park*, Chapter XX), contrasting with Elinor Dashwood's quiet commitment and Edward's sacrifice. Elinor's words, "*I could not be happy with a man whose taste did not in every point coincide with my own. He must enter in all my feelings; the same books, the same music must charm us both*" (*Sense and Sensibility*, Chapter VIII). This quote summarizes Austen's belief that emotional as well as intellectual harmony are very important for a successful marriage.

Triumph of Love Marriages

In the novels of Jane Austen, the process of courtship is portrayed as genuine as well as planned. Marianne's passionate outcry, "*Esteem him! Like him! Cold-hearted Elinor. Oh! worse than cold-hearted!*" (*Sense and Sensibility*, Chapter IV), dramatizes the tension between reason and feeling. Austen's portrayal of courtship rituals like the social prohibition that "*No young lady can justify in falling in love before the gentleman's love is declared*" (*Northanger Abbey*, Chapter XVII). This line exposes the performative nature of courtship in the nineteenth century England.

Women's need to attract a good husband through personality and behavior further illustrates marriage as both personal and social performance. Mrs. Jennings's declaration, "*if I don't get one of you at least well married before I have done with you, it shall not be my fault*" (*Sense and Sensibility*, Chapter XXV), shows the matchmaking pressure that drives females' behavior. Austen's lady protagonists navigate these cultural scripts cautiously but with an apparent proclamation of self-worth.

Austen's keen social observation exposes the larger judgmental norms regarding marriage. As Sir Thomas Bertram observes in *Mansfield Park*, "*there cannot be equalities*" between the daughters of Bertram and their poorer cousin Fanny, pointing to the rigid classism underlying matrimonial considerations (*Mansfield Park*, Chapter VII). Such distinctions shape social acceptance and marriage prospects, while *Northanger Abbey* humorously reveals these social structures as a "*numerous class of females, whose society can raise no other emotion than surprise at there being any men in the world who could like them well enough to marry them*" (*Northanger Abbey*, Chapter VIII).

Conclusion

Despite the societal and financial underpinnings, Austen's novels find hope in marriages grounded in mutual affection and understanding. Edward and Elinor's union, despite Edward's lack of

fortune after being disinherited, is a narrative triumph of love over materialism. Elizabeth's decision of marrying Mr. Darcy in *Pride and Prejudice* after she realizes her love for him also reflects the choice of female characters of Austen's novels. In *Sense and Sensibility*, Elinor reflects, "I will be calm. I will be mistress of myself." (Chapter IX), representing grace under emotional trial. Their relationship challenges the mercantile marriage ideal and suggests an alternative grounded in "prudence and honor" (*Sense and Sensibility*, Chapter 37).

Austen's novels intricately weave social critique with intimate portraits of love and marriage. Through her female protagonists' struggles, Austen challenges the mercenary reasons dominating marriage while sustaining the transformative power of love, respect, and compatibility. Her enduring legacy lies in illuminating marriage as a deeply personal quest conducted within the limits and pacts of the nineteenth century British society.

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